

Writing on the margins: graffiti in Italy

(seventh to sixteenth centuries)

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In all modern languages, the word 'graffiti' is associated with social criticism, protest and vandalism. On the contrary, what historians call graffiti is unrelated to transgression.

Nonetheless, contemporary and ancient graffiti share one important aspect: both are public writings produced spontaneously and beyond any control from authorities. The study of ancient graffiti allows us to get access to the worldview of individuals in the past. This explains the importance of considering graffiti as a historical source worthy of being studied alongside the conventional ones.

Graffiti as a historical source

The Graff-IT project aims to develop a new interdisciplinary approach to the study of medieval and Renaissance Italian graffiti (seventh to the sixteenth centuries) as a historical source to allow a correct contextualisation of graffiti within their space-time and social production frame. The project has several goals. First, it wants to give graffiti full dignity as written sources and asserts their study as intrinsic to the discipline of palaeography. By doing so, it also aims to overcome the atomistic approach to graffiti to identify new textualities and new languages. Another goal is to look at graffiti as a source of the history of devotional practices and signs of the socio-cultural

identity of people and places. Finally, but not less importantly, the project also aims to change our perception of historical artworks by shifting the focus from the creation stage to their social function and use over time.

The term 'graffito' is a modern invention made current in the archaeological lexicon only around the mid-nineteenth century. It derives from the Italian verb *graffiare*, 'to scratch', developed from the Latin *graphium*. Therefore, the word 'graffito' literally refers to the scratching technique of writing by means of a hard tip. However, by extended meaning, the term came to denote all forms of extemporaneous writings made on a surface not primarily intended for this purpose, regardless of the technique used. In this broad, commonly accepted definition, the focus is no longer on the writing tool but on the medium. The latter is undoubtedly an important aspect to consider, yet it does not suffice to cover the huge variety of forms of writing that may be defined as graffiti.

The writers

Besides the material aspects of writing, another crucial factor is the status of the

writer. Those who write graffiti on a wall, using a hard tip or a self-made brush and paint, do not operate upon someone's request or on commission. In this sense, graffiti are different from most medieval written sources, which were produced to satisfy the request of a commissioner, be it a religious or secular institution or a member of the elite. All being considered, graffiti are understood as follows in the Graff-IT project: graffiti is a form of writing, sometimes mixed with figurative patterns, made on a surface not primarily designed for this purpose by means of an occasional tool, regardless of the technique used and beyond the writer's dependency on an authority.

Marginality

Another key concept for the study of graffiti as envisaged in the Graff-IT project, relates to the term 'margin', which is charged with multiple meanings. The first one refers to both the physical space and the materiality of writing. From this viewpoint, the margin is understood as a place of encounter. The margins of book pages often contain notes left by readers, which bear witness to their personal encounters with the

Figure 1: Verona, Basilica of St. Zeno: chronicle graffiti on fourteenth century frescoes.

Figure 2: Spoleto (Perugia) – Church of St. Ponziano: graffiti on fourteenth century frescoes.

Figure 3: Piedicammoro (Perugia), Chapel of the Blessed Virgin: graffiti on fifteenth century frescoes.

texts written on those pages. Similarly, graffiti written on the margins of frescoes are evidence of a dialogue between the viewers and the painted scenes or figures, and sometimes, also with the formal inscriptions accompanying the figurative representations. Graffiti can also be written on the margins of painted

panels so as not to deface the figures depicted, thereby showing respect and conformity to the values expressed by the artwork. Recognising the margins as writing spaces disrupts our certainties about the alleged misappropriation of the surfaces and the adventitious and almost parasitic nature of graffiti.

Figure 4: Spoleto (Perugia) – Church of St. Ponziano: detail of a graffito reading «Bene e peggio chocha chi mai ama bisocha che po(r)tano fede pocha al mio parere».

